

D8.4. Report on Social acceptance of Biowaste Derived Products and Services

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Executive summary

The main aim of this document is to report on the social acceptance of new bioproducts and value chains of the VALUEWASTE project. This report summarizes the results from the data collection and includes conclusions from the analysis of that data and one workshop, highlighting opportunities.

The main purpose of performing these activities is to find answers to practical questions such as “Are people, in Spain and Denmark, aware of new technologies and resources and to what extent they are ready to accept new insect-, bacteria-based, or fertilizer products?”

One of the goals for the present Deliverable was to increase the number of participants, trying to reduce the difference between Danish and Spanish surveyed people. This fact was achieved as Danish participants increased by 87%, up to 225 people; whereas, Spanish participants were 279 at the end. This Deliverable enhances information provided in previous Deliverables’ results by increasing the number of responses (15% higher), adding examples, and providing data interpretation. This report thus complements existing Deliverables with a basis for the analytical approach.

The WP and Deliverable leader, SAVONIA, started the social acceptance context identification work with a series of interviews and small group discussions with companies, stakeholders, target groups and experts, which were reported, as part of D8.1 in February 2020 (M16), followed by the D 8.2 report in November 2020 (M25), and D8.3 on First insights on social acceptance, in June 2021 (M32). In addition, a survey questionnaire on social acceptance and social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) was developed in collaboration with Murcia (Spain) and

Kalundborg (Denmark) municipalities. As previously discussed, the number of responses in 2021 was lower than expected. Therefore, a second campaign was performed in April-May 2022, to increase the number of responses, reaching a total of 523 participants. Kalundborg, Murcia and the industry partners have actively participated in the survey content development and realisation, including actions to increase response rates, with language editions before launch. Answers were collected, and data analysed and managed according to the European GDPR legislation and ethical requirements as agreed on VALUEWASTE Protection of Personal Data D11.2 and Human participation (D11.4) Deliverables.

Insights on barriers, opportunities and challenges have been collected from stakeholder and expert interviews, survey questionnaires both at Murcia and Kalundborg municipalities, and from an expert workshop on Social Acceptance and S-LCA, which applied portfolio techniques for joint future scenario insights. CETENMA has brought S-LCA insights, as well as evaluated and given feedback to improve the report.

The main scope of the social acceptance survey questionnaire was to measure the public level of social acceptance of the citizens’ opinion about the VALUEWASTE products coming from the three value chains (protein ingredients and recycled plant nutrients). The present study divides the social acceptance into three different perspectives: socio-political acceptance, community acceptance and market acceptance. Overall, citizens have awareness, involvement, and willingness to adopt new bioproducts, being independent of age, gender, education level, or residence. They think that environmental factors, quality, and

prize are important factors, and it can be expected that the acceptance level will be high when these products enter the market. However, only few citizens have experienced new bioproducts from biowaste since they are not available at the market. Properties, like healthiness, nutritional value, quality, safety, prize and biowaste source are important for successful implementation of new bioproducts. At this point, it is interesting to mention that there were three hotspots found during the social acceptance analysis. These three hotspots were studied from the mentioned perspectives (socio-political, community and market acceptance). Four comparisons were performed according to the country (Denmark and Spain), gender (female and male), age (diverse age groups) and education level (diverse levels).

Awareness of citizens and their willingness to adopt new bioproducts give many opportunities that need to be considered when developing new business models for those bioproducts (Eskelinen et al., 2020). Hence, it is required to learn from the cultural and behavioural change use of alternative sources and new sustainable technology towards systemic change on circular

economy and increase the awareness and dissemination of the project impacts to the society and environment. All these identified opportunities are useful when designing value proposition of a business model. The results will be used when developing the circular economy business models of VALUEWASTE (D7.4.).

In this way, one of the crucial challenges to reach the market with these kinds of products is to change both the production and the behaviour. At this point, two questions may arise i) which is the vital behaviour to be changed? and ii) how can the dissemination be improved to provide better information to consumers?

Also, to study the complex factors of social acceptance, it can be concluded that a systematic process and workshop, enabling interaction, idea generation and assessment, helps and supports in decision making, and increases trust and social justice on actions.

Lastly, the need for sufficient enabling policies and the reduction in taxes and legal restrictions must be highlighted. Without proper policymaking, the VALUEWASTE project can be greatly hindered.

Content

1	INTRODUCTION	9
2	OBJECTIVES	10
3	METHODOLOGY	11
3.1	SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE INDICATOR CHARACTERIZATION METHOD AND COLOURING SYSTEM	13
4	RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	16
4.1	PARTICIPANT'S SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE	16
4.2	HOTSPOT IDENTIFICATION.....	18
4.3	SOCIO-POLITICAL ACCEPTANCE.....	20
4.4	COMMUNITY ACCEPTANCE.....	26
4.5	MARKET ACCEPTANCE.....	29
5	GENERAL DISCUSSION AND OVERVIEW OF RESULTS	34
6	CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	37
7	REFERENCES	38
8	ANNEX I. LIST OF QUESTIONS USED IN THE ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE.....	40
9	ANNEX II. THE VALUEWASTE SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE WITH BASIC REPORT ON SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE.....	44

List of figures

Figure 1: An example of visualizing data from the Excel table into Bar-graphs.....	14
Figure 2: Share of respondents according to country of residence.	16
Figure 3: Share of respondents according to education level.	17
Figure 4: Share of respondents according to age group.....	17
Figure 5: Share of respondents according to gender.....	18
Figure 6: Comparison between awareness on EU-policies by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).	21
Figure 7: Awareness on emerging technologies regarding biowaste and biowaste valorisation by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).	22
Figure 8: Awareness on new sustainable resources for production of food, feed and fertilizer by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).	23
Figure 9: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by country. ...	24
Figure 10: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by gender. ..	24
Figure 11: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by age.....	25
Figure 12: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by education level.	25
Figure 13: Citizens' involvement on day-to-day measures regarding climate change by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).....	26
Figure 14: Acceptance of sustainable, biowaste-based products by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).....	27
Figure 15: Comparison between acceptance of new, untested products and consumption of sustainable products already present in the market, according to country.....	28
Figure 16: Comparison between acceptance of new, untested products and consumption of sustainable products already present in the market, according to country.....	28
Figure 17. Comparison between acceptance of new, untested products and consumption of sustainable products already present in the market, according to age.	29
Figure 18: Comparison between acceptance of new, untested products and consumption of sustainable products already present in the market, according to education level.....	29
Figure 19: Importance of promotion properties of the proposed products by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).....	30
Figure 20: Importance of production properties of the proposed products by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).....	31
Figure 21: Importance of pricing properties of the new products by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).....	32
Figure 22: Importance of new product market by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).	33

List of tables

Table 1: Indicator and sub-indicator composition for social acceptance. Questions and their identification numbers can be consulted in Annex I.....	12
Table 2: An example of applying Excel tables for calculating average numbers and colouring the numbers.	13
Table 3: Scoring values of the main hotspots located with the survey answers and	

characterization phase.....	18
Table 4: Characterization for question number 60: “Please, rate the following statements on insect/bacteria-based recycled products: Would you agree to buy insects-based products because they are sustainably produced and reduce environmental emissions?”	20
Table 5: List of the questions that compose the survey, along with their identification number used in the analysis.	40
Table 6: question 1, country	44
Table 7: Answers given into text field:.....	45
Table 8: question 2, education level	46
Table 9: question 3, gender.....	47
Table 10: question 4, age group.....	48
Table 11: question 5, awareness.....	49
Table 12: question 6, agreement with statements	52
Table 13: question 7, measures against climate change	53
Table 14: question 8, options to palliate climate change	54
Table 15: question 9, agreement with the relevance (or lack of relevance) of different issues	56
Table 16: question 10, new protein or fertiliser sources preferences.....	58
Table 17: question 11, bought products	59
Table 18: question 12, agreement with an statement.....	60
Table 19: question 13, ingredients proprieties relevance	62
Table 20: question 14, statements relevance	63
Table 21: question 15, statements rating	65
Table 22: question 16, how the EU Commission should motivate customers	67

1 Introduction

VALUEWASTE develops new solutions, bioproducts from biowaste, and value chains. The VALUEWASTE project proposes an integrated approach in urban biowaste upcycling to produce high-value bio-based products, developing the first complete solution to fully valorise biowaste across Europe. Three value chains -microbial and insect proteins, and recycled nutrients - use urban biowaste side-streams as raw material for its valorisation. VALUEWASTE is developed at two very different European locations, Murcia (Spain) and Kalundborg (Denmark) with the purpose of finding solutions both technically and socially adopted to the different socio-economic contexts.

The business cases aim to find new solutions and valorising models from urban biowaste, thus being sustainable solutions linked to a smaller amount of greenhouse gas emissions, which enhance self-sufficiency in protein and fertilizer production. New ways of producing protein and fertilizers from waste, creating circular economy valorising models. Social acceptance and behavioural change are an important part of sustainable development, which is essential when designing new valorising and business models and when introducing the new products into the market (Planing et al., 2015). For this reason, the work on social acceptance at VALUEWASTE, reported here, is closely integrated to the business cases and models.

Target 12.3 of the Sustainable Development Goals agenda calls for countries to: “halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses”, by 2030. This goal may be achievable if production and consumption practices change (Beretta et al., 2013; UNEP 2020). Consumers’ behaviour can be influenced based on command-and-control, market-based or voluntary change approaches (UNEP, 2020). Consumers are more averse to command-and-control and market-based measures (also because these are often poorly communicated), making policy makers more inclined to rely on voluntary change. There is little evidence that voluntary behavioural change contributes to significant changes in overall consumer behaviour. Information tools do yield responses, though on modest scales. This highlights the need to improve carbon literacy levels in the wider population to change social norms. Information tools can be optimized to increase their efficiency by considering the complexity of consumer psychology, including gender norms (UNEP, 2020).

Socioeconomic and behavioural aspects, together with social acceptance, need to be studied when introducing such new solutions into the market. As mentioned in the previous deliverable (D8.3 First insights on social acceptance), some studies have demonstrated how consuming insects (as a whole or powder) show significant benefits in terms of protein content (Rumpold and Schluter, 2013; van Huis, 2013; Halloran et al., 2015). However, the social acceptance is still very low in Western societies (van Huis, 2013, Hartmann and Siegrist, 2017). Amato (2017) also reported this fact (barriers to insect-based foods in western societies), together with potential drivers that might lead to a change in eating habits. This helps to understand whether and to what extent consumers are willing to accept insects (or their components) in their diets which is crucial information when estimating how to organize the food chain towards the introduction of insect-based ingredients in Western diets.

SAVONIA started the social acceptance context identification work with a series of interviews

and small group discussions with the companies, stakeholders, target groups and experts. This task was reported in February 2020 (M16 as part of D8.1), in November 2020 (M25, D8.2 report) and in June, 2021 (M32, D8.3 – First insights on social acceptance). This latter deliverable is a public report which can be found on the project website (<https://valuewaste.eu/available-material/>).

A survey questionnaire on social acceptance and S-LCA was developed in collaboration with Murcia (Spain) and Kalundborg (Denmark) municipalities. Since the number of responses in 2021 was lower than estimated, a second campaign was performed in April-May 2022 to increase the number of responses. In both cases, answers were collected, and data analysed and managed according to the European GDPR legislation and ethical requirements as agreed on VALUEWASTE Protection of Personal Data (POPD; D11.2) and Human participation (H, D11.4) documents.

As mentioned in D8.3 – First insights on social acceptance, the social acceptance of the proposed solutions that aim to tackle the afore-mentioned issues is highly important as it can determine their success. The present study presents the social acceptance measured through three perspectives: socio-political acceptance, community acceptance and market acceptance (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007).

2 Objectives

The objective of this deliverable is to report to the public the social acceptance of the new bioproducts obtained through the VALUEWASTE solution. This report summarizes the results from the analysis of the information collected and the workshop, including conclusions and highlighting opportunities. This study considers the three dimensions of social acceptance: socio-political, market, and community acceptance. Evaluating these dimensions, it is possible to highlight opportunities and potential points of conflict (hotspots) that may arise within the social acceptance, as well as illustrate the profile of the potentially most willing participant, taking into consideration country of residence, age, gender and education level.

These goals are achieved by following the context, definitions and course of action defined in the previous deliverable D8.3.

3 Methodology

As explained in the previous deliverable (D8.3), the information on social acceptance is gathered through a survey directed at the citizens of Kalundborg (Denmark) and Murcia (Spain), by interviews to stakeholders, and an expert workshop. The design, distribution, collection and evaluation of the survey is discussed in the aforementioned deliverable.

The previous Deliverable 8.3 reported 456 survey replies. This result was lower than expected; thus, it was required to increase the number of participants, improving the quality of data; better representativeness. This step was performed by arranging interviews with both city representatives as an effort to reach out to more people and explore the process of inviting new citizens to the questions in the survey.

In Kalundborg, the survey was distributed through personal contacts and social media, which was the most effective way. In Murcia, visits to schools complemented the methods used during the first campaign (social media, press releases and a QR code on the project street totems and billboards). During subsequent weeks, the survey gathered 67 new responses, about 87% from Denmark, which brought the share of both countries (Spain and Denmark) closer to each other. The previous Deliverable 8.3 showed 167 Danish participants and 273 Spanish, which represented 36.6% and 59.9% of the total number of respondents, respectively. The rest of participants lived in other countries. The new set of participants increased from 456 to 523 (near 15% higher), improving the percentage of Danish respondents from 36.6% to 43.0% (225 people), closer to the final figure of 53.3% Spanish respondents (279 people). Overall, the number of responses increased which resulted in a better balance between the two municipalities.

The number of participants younger than the age of 18 was low, as only 4 participants declared this to be their age. Thus, for the analysis of results, it is worth keeping in mind the small sample size for this age group, and that the information gathered from this age group is not as representative as other age groups.

To simplify the analysis of the present study due to the large number of responses (523 replies) and questions asked, a coding system was applied. The survey consisted of 17 questions and a total of 70 possible answers. Thus, a new data file was generated, with the coded questions and answers (please refer to Annex I).

Initially, the analysis was initiated with Webropol 3.0 platform results, an electronic survey system which is used to create, collect, and analyse surveys. Webropol is available to students and staff members at SAVONIA.

The first social acceptance category, socio-political acceptance, includes the broadest level of knowledge appealing to accept or reject the subject of policies and technologies, while moving from global to local. In Annex I, these questions are between numbers 8-22 and 28-40. Moreover, the survey distinguishes policies and technologies towards different stakeholders, including the EU, customers, farmers, and producers, as well as objectives, such as general (policy) aims, insect-based products and biowaste utilisation as resource. Thus, questions are categorised into larger number of groups, including these sub-groups for more easy and reliable analysis.

The second category, community acceptance, refers to decisions that have time dimensions, such as distribution, procedures, and trust. These questions are 23-27 and 41-48 (Annex I), creating a group describing and measuring community aspect. Subgroups contain questions concerning procedures, trust, and distribution of the benefits from the consumer's point of view.

Finally, the third category, market acceptance, explains market adoption of innovations by focusing not only on consumer's but also on investor's needs (Moula et al., 2021). Questions 49-69 (Annex I) create the group, including questions about the four P's of marketing mix (Kotler et al., 2010): Promotion, Production, Price and Placement.

Hence, three indicator groups were created, including several explanatory sub-groups that help to describe and measure the three dimensions of social acceptance.

Table 1: Indicator and sub-indicator composition for social acceptance. Questions and their identification numbers can be consulted in Annex I.

Indicator	Sub-indicator	Explanation	Questions
Socio-Political acceptance	EU-policy:	Awareness of the EU targets to become climate neutral	8,16,31,32,37,38,39,40
	Technology:	Awareness of modern technologies for new products	9,13,28,29,30,33,34,35,36
	Resources:	Awareness of resources for new products	10,11,12,14,15
	Biowaste:	Awareness of Biowaste appliance	17,18,19,20,21,22
Community acceptance	Procedures:	Measures taken for climate change	23,24,25,26,27
	Trust:	Consent to accept new products	41,42,43,44,45,46, 60, 63, 64
	Distribution:	Practical application of new products	47,48
Market acceptance	Promotion:	Properties of the new products	49,51,54,55,56,58,
	Production:	Source of raw material of new products	50,52,53,59,62,65,66
	Price:	Pricing of the new products	57,61
	Placement:	Market placement of the new products	67,68,69

3.1 Social acceptance indicator characterization method and colouring system

The survey questions were qualitative in nature. This made it essential to establish a method for quantifying the responses regarding each social indicator to illustrate social acceptance and help locate potential hotspots. Thus, a scoring system was developed, based on the type of question, following the methodology proposed by Azimi et al. (2020).

In the case of single-choice questions, where a statement was given and participants declared their affinity (i.e., from strongly disagree to strongly agree), a Likert scale was applied. For the most favourable answer a score of 5 was assigned; whereas, the least favourable option, a score of 1. Then, the average score was calculated considering the respective percentage share of each answer given.

Question 57 (Annex I), “Would you buy the insect/bacteria-based product because of rich vitamin and mineral content?”, is taken as an explanatory example:

- Strongly agree; Value 5; 28.6% of respondents chose this option (0.286 x 5).
- Agree; Value 4; 44.2% of respondents chose this option (0.442 x 4).
- Neither agree nor disagree: Value 3; 22.1% of respondents chose this option (0.221 x 3).
- Disagree: Value 2; 4.1% of respondents chose this option (0.041 x 2).
- Strongly disagree: Value 1; 0.9% of respondents chose this option (0.009 x 1).

Now each value is assigned to the obtained percentages and add them together, resulting on an average score. Taking the answers from respondents from Denmark:

$$0.286 \times 5 + 0.442 \times 4 + 0.221 \times 3 + 0.041 \times 2 + 0.009 \times 1 = 3.95$$

In this case, the question would yield an average score of 3.95, in a range from 1 to 5, for the question 57 from Denmark respondents. Afterwards, this average number is placed in a table matching the question 57 for Denmark (please refer to the number 3.95).

This procedure was repeated for Spain. Afterwards, according to grouping parameters, for example Pricing of new products, question 61 was considered. These operations were repeated, and a weighted value was obtained for each group. Finally, the average between these two numbers was calculated (Table 2).

Table 2: An example of applying Excel tables for calculating average numbers and colouring the numbers.

	Question 57	Question 61	Average
Denmark	3.95	3.05	3.50
Spain	3.98	3.04	3.51

As further explained below, Table 2 also indicates colours which helps data interpretation: the greener – the more positive answers are given. However, since such tables include 69 questions together with 13 parameters, such as 2 countries, 2 genders, 5 age levels and 4 education levels, it was also decided to visualise the average results by plotting them using bar-graphs. The bar-graph (Figure 1: *An example of visualizing data from the Excel table into Bar-graphs.*) equivalent to Table 2 can be found below.

Figure 1: An example of visualizing data from the Excel table into Bar-graphs.

For yes-no questions, the amount of favourable and unfavourable answers was taken into consideration. The affirmative answer is a favourable option and the negatory is unfavourable. The score is calculated similarly to single-choice questions, considering the favourable answer similar to “strongly disagree” i.e., given a score of 5, and the unfavourable option as “strongly disagree”, and given a score of 1. N/A answers were not taken into account, and the score was calculated out using affirmative/negative answers only. An example is provided as follows for any given yes/no question:

- 30.0% Positive answer: 5 (0.3 x 5)
- 55.0% Negative answer: 1 (0.55 x 1)
- 15.0% n/a (0.15)

Using these response percentages, the score for this question would be of 2.41 using the following calculation:

$$(0.3 \times 5 + 0.55 \times 1) / (1 - 0.15) = 2.41$$

Consequently, the global score for each social indicator as a function of the social acceptance indicator was produced, considering all sub-indicators equal in weight.

In summary, the answer options for the question posed come as follows:

For questions: 12-22, 28-47, 49, and 61-69:

- 1 – strongly disagree
- 2 – disagree
- 3 – neither agree nor disagree
- 4 – agree
- 5 – strongly agree

For questions: 50-59

- 1 – not important at all
- 2 – not much importance
- 3 – neutral
- 4 – some importance
- 5 – very high importance

For questions: 8-11, 23-27, and 48

- 1 – no
- 5 – yes

For the sake of clarification, a score of 4.09 means that an average weighted score lies between “agree” and “strongly agree”, or between “some importance” and “very high importance”.

The last section of the survey was not considered for the scoring of the social acceptance as participants provided their comments or suggestions. These comments were grouped into categories (i.e., general complaints, suggestions, etc.) to help to draw conclusions.

As introduced above, a colouring system was applied to rapidly detect potential hotspots. This was inspired by the methodology proposed by Cirotto and Franze (2011). This method consists of assigning a colour to the value ranges obtained with the scoring system. The hue of each indicator is proportional to its score, where lower values (i.e., closer to 1) tend to red, higher values tend to green (i.e., closer to 5), and neutral values tend to yellow. In the present study, a colour gradient was applied, to increase the accuracy of the assessment of social acceptance indicators.

In the present deliverable, results (other than hotspot identification) are mostly illustrated with graphs, as the data matrices generated from the analysis of the scores for each question are too large and do not represent the findings as effectively as graphs. Should the readers need to consult the tables generated from the survey, they can be made available upon request to SAVONIA (tuomo.eskelinen@savonia.fi; [mailto](mailto:tuomo.eskelinen@savonia.fi)) and CETENMA (martin.soriano@cetenma.es).

The methodology on the interviews (questions and stakeholders addressed) and expert workshop on social acceptance and S-LCA, applying Prospective Rapid Impact Assessment (PRIA) foresight workshop and tools (Eskelinen et al., 2021) were described in the previous deliverable 8.3, First Insights on Social Acceptance. The workshop was organised online for the VALUEWASTE experts. Online tools for idea generation on social impacts and acceptance, multicriteria (MC) online evaluation, portfolio decision analysis (PDA) and results presentation in a PRIA frame were used and applied (Eskelinen et al, 2021). The results include the identification of future actions and opportunities.

4 Results and discussion

In this Section, the findings on social acceptance of the VALUEWASTE products and value chains are displayed. As previously mentioned, the analysis includes the three dimensions (socio-political acceptance, community acceptance, and market acceptance), beside the sociodemographic profile of each participant (nationality, age, gender, and education level) and the hotspot identification.

4.1 Participant's sociodemographic profile

Upon the closure of the survey on May 16th, 2022, there were a total of 523 responses.

From a total number of respondents, 225 (43%) were from Denmark, and 279 (53%) from Spain. 19 answers (4%) were received from residents from other countries, including Australia, Belgium, Chile, Colombia, Estonia, France, Germany, Greece, Greenland, Italy, Poland, United Kingdom, and the USA (Share of respondents according to country of residence.).

Figure 2: Share of respondents according to country of residence.

Figure 3: Share of respondents according to education level.

Regarding the age group (Figure 4: Share of respondents according to age group), 42% of the answers were received from the age group of 31-45 years, and 35% from the group of 46-64 years. The group of 18-30 years represented 18% percentage of answers. Four young people below 18 completed the survey, corresponding with 1% of all respondents. As mentioned in the previous Section, this should be taken into consideration, as this age group's representation is quite lower than the rest of age groups. Only 2 respondents decided not to disclose their age group.

Figure 4: Share of respondents according to age group

Gender wise (Figure 5: Share of respondents according to gender), a total of 204 surveys were completed by male respondents, and 317 from females. The remaining two respondents decided not to disclose their gender.

Figure 5: Share of respondents according to gender

4.2 Hotspot identification

The characterization of the survey responses and the application of the colouring system yielded clear results in terms of hotspots and potential points of conflict that may hinder social acceptance. In total, only 3 questions (26, 48, 65) received an average score lower than 3.0, of the 69 questions asked (see Annex I), with the lowest score (1.58) found for Q48; whereas, the score for Q26 and Q65 was 2.90 and 2.76, respectively. Thus, these are the questions to be analysed in this Section.

Table 3: Scoring values of the main hotspots located with the survey answers and characterization phase.

	Question 26	Question 48	Question 65
Denmark	2.95	1.83	2.42
Spain	2.97	1.67	2.56
Female	2.90	1.68	2.36
Male	3.13	1.87	2.69
Younger than 18	5.00	1.00	3.00
Ages 18-30	3.72	1.67	2.40
Ages 31-45	2.90	1.76	2.42
Ages 46-65	2.73	1.85	2.60
Older than 65	2.33	1.40	2.60
Elementary/High School	3.92	1.31	2.12
Technical/Vocational program	2.25	1.73	2.62
Bachelor	2.94	1.71	2.54
Master/PhD	3.14	1.85	2.47

Question 26 is phrased as follows: “Do you take any kind of measures to palliate the climate change?” If the response is yes, there was another question: “c) If yes to previous, do you take these measures to palliate the climate change: I use the public transport or alternative transport (bike, electric scooter, skateboard, roller skates etc)”. According to the low score obtained for this question, it can be extracted that the citizen involvement is not optimal as, ideally, if citizens were fully committed to sustainability, more respondents would have responded favourably to this question. However, in some cases, the use of public or alternative transport is not feasible for reasons such as distance or practicality.

In Table 3 it can be also observed that all participants younger than the age of 18 use sustainable methods of transportation. However, this cannot be computed as favourable since the driver’s license can only be attained past the age of 18, meaning that quite possibly participants use sustainable mean of transport since no other option is viable for them. Saying so, the majority of participants of the ages 18 to 30 also use more sustainable methods of transportation. Therefore, the takeaway message is that younger generations are generally more favourable to use sustainable methods of transportation compared to older generations.

Question 48 is phrased as follows: “Have you bought products which contain insect/bacteria-based products, for example, protein bars or protein powder?”. Most participants declared they did not consume any insect or bacteria-based products. While this practice is common in several countries around the world, this is not the case in most European countries according to previous studies (Huis et al., 2013). Moreover, these products do not have a significant presence in the European market or in western diets. Despite this, interest in insect-based food is increasing (Kröger et al., 2022). This is in line with the survey findings (question 60), where participants in the survey reported they were generally willing to consume these types of products (Table 3). This means that, although the current consumption of these products is low, there is a high interest in exploring these new types of foods.

Table 4: Characterization for question number 60: "Please, rate the following statements on insect/bacteria-based recycled products: Would you agree to buy insects-based products because they are sustainably produced and reduce environmental emissions?"

Socio-demographic group	Question 60
Denmark	3.53
Spain	3.65
Female	3.55
Male	3.70
Younger than 18	3.00
Ages 18-30	3.73
Ages 31-45	3.69
Ages 46-65	3.51
Older than 65	3.50
Elementary	3.78
Technical	3.41
Bachelor	3.69
Master/PhD	3.68
Average	3.57

Questions 65 is phrased as follows: "Would you be willing to pay more on recycled plant nutrients for crop production because their cause less environmental effects like carbon emissions?". On average, this question obtained a score of 2.76, slightly below neutrality. This indicates that, on average, participants are unwilling to pay more for these types of products. This resonates with the finding that participants value price, as price is a major factor when choosing products (see Section 4.5).

4.3 Socio-political acceptance

Socio-political acceptance is the priority of this project as it effectively fosters and enhances market and community acceptance. The survey addresses the problem of socio-political acceptance in questions 8-22 and 28-40 (Annex I) where information concerns acceptance through a socio-political perspective.

As shown in Table 1, socio-political acceptance is comprised of four different awareness indicators, explaining overall, broad, and general levels of social acceptance (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). The survey includes these questions converging overall EU targets towards Sustainability, Technology, Resources, and Biowaste.

Figure (Figure 6 A) shows awareness of EU-policy by country comprising average of weighted values of the answers for the group of questions 8, 16, 31, 32, 37, 38, 39, and 40. Denmark responds 4.36 and Spain 4.21 out of 5.00. The difference of the EU aims acceptance between these countries is negligible. Therefore, it can be inferred that respondents from both Denmark and Spain find EU-policies clearly understandable, highly agreeing on general environmental and socio-economic issues.

A similar result can be inferred from the awareness on EU-policies from both genders (Figure 6B). In other words, there is no important difference of awareness of the EU-policies between

men and women.

The same indicator from the perspective of age groups (Figure 6C) and education levels (Figure 6D). As it can be extracted from Figure 8C, all groups except non-adults (i.e., respondents below the age of 18) presented a similar level of acceptance. Participants below the age of 18 differ from the rest groups, at first glance. However, it is not possible to draw conclusions out of this comparison due to the very low absolute number of respondents (only four persons out of 523 under 18 years old). Awareness on EU-policies by education level presented a similar distribution of results with no-significant differences observed between these four groups (Figure 8D).

Figure 6: Comparison between awareness on EU-policies by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).

Figure 7 demonstrates almost no difference of awareness between countries (Figure 7A) and genders (Figure 7B). Similarly, it can be observed that there were no differences among the age groups (Figure 7C). Whereas a slightly lower level of awareness between Elementary & Vocational levels of education and Bachelor & Master levels (Figure 7D). This fact can be considered logical due to higher maturity and involvement in social life among respondents obtaining Bachelor & Master education levels, including general awareness on wider socio-political aspects.

Figure 7: Awareness on emerging technologies regarding biowaste and biowaste valorisation by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).

Figure 8 shows the awareness on new sustainable resources for production of food, feed and fertilizer by country, gender, age, and education level. As observed, the awareness on biowaste valorisation technologies does not greatly vary between nationalities, age groups, genders, or education levels.

Figure 8: Awareness on new sustainable resources for production of food, feed and fertilizer by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).

Regarding awareness of biowaste properties and sustainable resources used for creation of new products, it can be inferred that the picture is in general similar to previous indicators: almost all groups of respondents provide analogous results. As shown in *Figure 9: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by country.*, the difference between countries is not significant, but the average awareness for biowaste is lower than for resources. This means that respondents (proportionally equal in both countries) express less knowledge towards the biowaste aspect than to resource aspect. More detailed research may be required about general information concerning biowaste for both countries.

Figure 9: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by country.

The same situation can be seen from another perspective when results are compared by gender (Figure 10: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by gender.). Both genders depict equally lower involvement towards biowaste aspect, compared to resource aspect.

Figure 10: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by gender.

A similar situation is found in the comparison between biowaste and resources awareness by age frames (Figure 11: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by age.). Given the fact that respondents below the age of 18 numbered four, the effect size of this group is very small.

Figure 11: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by age.

As it can be observed in *Figure 12: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by education level.*, the same comparison between indicators according to education level depicts analogous conclusions.

Figure 12: Comparison between biowaste and sustainable resources awareness by education level.

To sum up, the situation of socio-political acceptance of the new products is positive as all groups (except for the age group younger than 18 years of age) scored close or above 4.0 on all indicators. It can be interpreted that citizens show a high level of knowledge and involvement towards EU-aims, new technologies, and resources for making new products. Knowledge concerning biowaste, though also high, scored lower than the rest. In the specific case of VALUEWASTE related topics, it could be improved by the performance of awareness campaigns concerning the use of biowaste as a resource for food, feed and fertilizer, separate collection of biowaste, contribution of society for more sustainable use of biowaste, and providing more

information on waste management issues to the general population.

4.4 Community acceptance

Community acceptance is explained by the acceptance and social justice, as well as general trust by the community (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). In the survey, people could express their attitude towards these parameters. Questions 23,24,25,26, and 27 were designed to measure respondent's new products acceptance and followed effects on climate change. Questions 41,42,43,44,45, and 46 addressed people's consent to accept new products, when those become available on the market. Finally, questions 47 and 48 addressed the personal practice of consuming insect or bacteria-based products, already present in the market. These three groups of questions illustrated the full performance of community acceptance of the proposed new products.

Figure 13 shows that there is almost no difference between groups. Respondents in any category show a very high involvement in day-to-day measures against climate change.

Figure 13: Citizens' involvement on day-to-day measures regarding climate change by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).

Figure 14 illustrates a moderately high willingness to choose new food and feed protein products

when they appear on the market. Again, no difference between the groups is observed, except for participants of age below 18.

Figure 14: Acceptance of sustainable, biowaste-based products by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).

From Figure 15: Comparison between acceptance of new, untested products and consumption of sustainable products already present in the market, according to country. to Figure 18, it can be observed that participants acceptance of new products was high. These figures show a small difference of new product acceptance between those not yet appeared on the market and those appeared and tested by the respondents. Each pair of bars in the graphs represent new products not yet tested (the left bar) and new products already tested by respondents (the right bar).

As it can be deduced from the graphs, a slightly higher trust is displayed to already existing biowaste and sustainable products, which have been already tested. It is worth mentioning that respondents below 18 years are very active at “already-tested” categories (right-handed graphs). That means, this group tests new products more frequently than any other age group. At the same time, they are more suspicious of new products (left-handed graphs) than any other age group.

Meanwhile, the community acceptance of VALUEWASTE products is at very high level, among all the groups, where even young respondents represent their highest involvement. Hence, it

can be indicated that community' readiness to accept new food and feed products from biowaste produced by using insects or bacteria are at high level.

Figure 15: Comparison between acceptance of new, untested products and consumption of sustainable products already present in the market, according to country.

Figure 16: Comparison between acceptance of new, untested products and consumption of sustainable products already present in the market, according to country.

Figure 17. Comparison between acceptance of new, untested products and consumption of sustainable products already present in the market, according to age.

Figure 18: Comparison between acceptance of new, untested products and consumption of sustainable products already present in the market, according to education level.

4.5 Market acceptance

Social acceptance also requires the interpretation of market acceptance as the process of an adoption of marketing parameters of new products (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). Market acceptance focuses on consumer's level of satisfaction and the criteria for the acceptance of the products. Questions 49-69 were designed to get insights on the market acceptance, from the point of view of four-Ps of marketing mix: production, price, placement, and promotion. From Figure 19 to Figure 22, the importance of every parameter and its effect on the market acceptance are shown.

Figure 19 illustrates respondent's evaluation of promotion properties, such as information, functionality, aesthetics, image, specific environmental and social properties of new products.

Questions 49, 51, 52, 55, 56 and 58 gave answers to these properties of new products.

Figure 19: Importance of promotion properties of the proposed products by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).

Regarding the production properties of market acceptance (Figure 20), these had the highest importance for the respondents. These properties are taste, technical quality, high vitamins and mineral contents, as well as sustainable production with reduced environmental emissions. Questions 50, 52, 53, 59, 62 and 66 were designed to measure respondent's values concerning the importance of production properties of new products. According to previous references (Rumpold and Langen, 2020), the taste of products was found to be the most important factor for the acceptance of insect-based food.

Figure 20: Importance of production properties of the proposed products by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).

It can be observed (Figure 21) how respondents value the price for new products. The survey asks only two questions 57 and 61 for describing the attitude towards price levels. Participants were asked if they find price level important for the new products, and if they are willing to buy these products at a higher price level. On average, participants are close to neutral when asked to pay more for this type of products (see Section 4.2). Thus, price is important for citizens, but also the quality properties of new products.

Figure 21: Importance of pricing properties of the new products by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).

Placement property (Figure 22), or motivation steps taken by authorities by means of changing overall policies, including taxation, regulation and other social benefits, had a diverse practical meaning and it obtains important goal on the need for special activities to motivate customers from the government level. Placement property activities were of high importance and as they provide extra benefits to the public, such as lowering taxes and reducing inhibitory regulations. At some level these activities may create anti-effect conditions on the society.

Figure 22: Importance of new product market by country (A), gender (B), age (C) and education level (D).

5 General discussion and overview of results

As discussed, the social acceptance has been studied with a survey questionnaire from Murcia and Kalundborg respondents. The number of respondents of the survey questionnaire (n=523) has been increased and is higher than in a preliminary report (D8.3), giving better source for a quantitative analysis. A total of 118 respondents (49 from Spain, and 69 from Denmark) gave also verbal feedback, 33 of those agreed with the VALUEWASTE approach to deal with the challenges. As an alternative, several respondents suggested vegetable proteins as sustainable protein sources.

With the survey data analysis (Section 4), it can be estimated that there is a generally favourable outlook towards new, sustainable bioproducts from biowaste. General awareness of the issues and challenges which the VALUEWASTE project aims to tackle is high, as well as awareness on current aims and technologies at EU level. Moreover, it was observed that participants were relatively eager to try and buy food, feed and fertilisers made from biowaste, although they placed a higher trust in products already available in the market. Moreover, it was found that citizens valued greatly the qualities of the product, such as taste, technical and nutritional qualities. Finally, it was found that political involvement is key to the success of the project objectives, as inhibitory laws, and regulations, as well as taxes, must be reduced and awareness campaigns raised, to gather the attention of the general population.

Overall, the differences in social acceptance between the Danish municipality of Kalundborg and the Spanish municipality of Murcia were low. Similarly, factors such as age, gender and education level also did not significantly influence awareness, involvement or willingness in sustainability and social acceptance of the solutions proposed in this project. These findings are partially in contrast with results obtained from a study on the acceptance of the consumption of insects for food between Portugal and Spain, carried out by Ribeiro et al. (2022). In that study, the authors concluded there was a difference in acceptance between cultures and age ranges. However, the difference appreciated was not highly significant.

The findings in the present study align with the review prepared by Kröger et al. (2022), where it was determined that western societies are increasingly interested in the consumption of food that is derived from insects. Also, the obtained results align with the study by Popoff et al. (2017), whose report investigated the attitudes of both consumers and producers toward the use of insect-based ingredients to feed Scottish salmon in the UK. The study showed that only 10% of the 180 respondents were against including insect proteins in salmon feed. In addition, 75% of the respondents claimed that feeding salmon with insect ingredients would not affect their willingness to buy the fish. However, this was only for fish reared with vegetable waste, and other types of waste could have a more marked effect.

In general, citizens agreed that environmental factors are important, and it can be expected that the acceptance level will be high when these products enter to the market. In this way and according to Thomson and Joyse (2008) and Thomson and Boutilier (2011), it can be anticipated citizen acceptance level of “approval” with some products. However, only a low proportion of citizens have been exposed to novel bioproducts as they are not highly available in the market.

Product safety and legislation are key components in achieving social acceptance. Novel foods,

(e.g., bioproducts coming from insects), need authorization from the European Commission. The safety of such novel food is assessed, upon request by the Commission, by the European Food Safety Authority, EFSA (EU, 2015).

To achieve market acceptance, according to the obtained results, there are indications that people would like to buy products with bioproducts having healthy properties. The driver for change of customer behaviour can be related to attractive novel products and circular value chains, better use of biowaste, sustainability, and adaptation to climate change related to positive impacts from a point of view of water scarcity and soil degradation. However, the market is not ready for these new bioproducts. There are factors which may increase socio-political, and community acceptance. For example, creation of new jobs, attractive business of sustainability, better local resilience, less CO₂ emissions, and the development of more sustainable society.

The social acceptance analysis was completed with information provided by previous interviews and expert workshop. Such experiences provided production and value chain point of views, which tried to anticipate to the future both from the consumer and production point of views. In general, the social acceptance interviews and expert workshop (D8.3; Eskelinen et al., 2021) produced a joint view of social acceptance based on, firstly, policy makers point of view; secondly, producers & value chain point of view: opinion of the producer on the social acceptance or social impact from the value chain point of view; and thirdly, consumer or citizen point of view. These results can be seen as opportunities for the future: Firstly, an opportunity lays on the cultural and traditional change on the consumer, who decides whether he/she likes the end products from biowaste.

Tools to reach this are awareness raising through different campaigns and capacity building, and dissemination on the impacts. Secondly, an opportunity is in the use of technology and alternative materials as resource, to make the circular economy solutions possible. This opportunity also includes waste decrease. Thirdly, sustainability and environmental benefits are also opportunities for the future. A fourth opportunity lays in the adaptation of legislation, and EU policy which could help new bioproducts enter the market. The expert interviews indicate some market acceptance opportunities: supermarket chains, retailers, and companies selling feed, fertilizers, and pesticides to the agricultural sector, as well as business to business.

Workshop and interview results represent mainly the value chains (producers) and experts, and the viewpoints from the consumer, citizen, and policy makers indirectly through the expertise of the participants. The survey, on the other hand, produced insights on the consumer, and citizen point of views. The policy makers need to be addressed in further steps during and beyond the VALUEWASTE project.

According to the Deliverable 8.3, one important learning from the expert workshop is, that an interaction between the different stakeholders and actors is required to understand the complex variables of social impacts and affecting social acceptance. The PRIA approach used, combining multicriteria decision making (MCDS), and portfolio analysis (PDA; Kajanus et al., 2014, Eskelinen et al., 2017; Eskelinen et al., 2021), provides a systematic way to gather insights into 6 categories, and the evaluation made by the participants against relevant criteria supports both discussion and prioritization of ideas, their weaknesses, strengths, actions, and opportunities.

The Prospective Rapid Impact Assessment (PRIA) approach enables every participant to give their opinions, which increases social justice, and trust on the process. When evaluating social acceptance and impacts of products and value chains, PRIA is a fair method and approach since it increases justice and interaction as part of decision making.

6 Conclusions and recommendations

Overall, the social acceptance surveys and the subsequent characterization of the acceptance indicators point towards a high degree of social acceptance of VALUEWASTE products and services and could be englobed within the “approval” level of the social license ladder proposed by Thomson and Boutilier (2017). It can be thus concluded that the VALUEWASTE products and services, and the social and environmental issues it presents, will be accepted by society.

No major difference in social acceptance between age groups, genders, nationalities, and education levels is observed. The only exception is participants younger than 18 years of age, but they were only represented by 4 participants. This indicates that awareness, involvement, and willingness in sustainability are independent of the background of the citizens, demonstrating a clear opportunity, since all groups are keen on participating in the innovative model of sustainable consumption.

The main scope of the social acceptance survey questionnaire was to measure the public level of social acceptance of the three value chains which produce new biowaste valorizing products and services or technologies. Overall, the citizens have awareness and interest in new bioproducts like protein ingredients and recycled plant nutrients. They think that environmental factors, quality, and prize are important factors, and it can be expected that the acceptance level will be high when these products enter to the market. However, only few citizens have experienced new bioproducts from biowaste since they are not available at the market.

Awareness of citizens and their willingness to adopt new bioproducts give many opportunities when developing new business models (Eskelinen et al., 2020): learning from the cultural and behavioural change, and use of alternative sources and new sustainable technology towards systemic change on circular economy and increase of awareness and dissemination on the impacts to the society and environment. All these identified opportunities are useful when designing value proposition of a business model, and the results will be used when developing the circular economy business models of VALUEWASTE. Also, another goal was to gain understanding on the complex factors affecting consumer behaviour and sustainable food system. The consumer behaviour can be influenced based on command-and-control, market-based or voluntary change approaches. It is needed to change both the production and the behaviour. The key question is, which is the vital behaviour we need to change (Grenny et al., 2013). Also, how can we improve with the consumer getting better information.

A central factor for the success of the project is related to the properties of the products, as participants deemed properties such as taste (for food), nutritional value, etc., to be highly important (Rumpold and Langen, 2020).

Also, to study the complex factors of social acceptance, it can be concluded, that a systematic process and workshop, enabling interaction, idea generation and assessment, helps and supports in decision making, and increases trust and social justice on actions.

Lastly, the need for sufficient enabling policies and the reduction in taxes and legal restrictions must be highlighted. Without proper policymaking, the VALUEWASTE project can be greatly hindered.

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8 Annex I. List of questions used in the analysis of social acceptance

The present annex shows the list of questions to perform the social acceptance analysis of the VALUEWASTE project.

Table 5: List of the questions that compose the survey, along with their identification number used in the analysis.

Nr	Questions
1	Answer time (hidden due to low significance of info)
2	Language (hidden due to low significance of info)
3	Country of residence
4	Country of residence Open text answers (hidden due to a combination with previous answer)
5	Education level
6	Gender
7	Age group
8	Are you aware that the EU aims to be climate-neutral by 2050 – an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions (CO ₂). All parts of society and economic sectors will play a role – from the power sector to industry, mobility, buildings, agriculture and forestry
9	Are you aware that Technologies using insects for protein production can cause less greenhouse gas emissions than traditional methods
10	Are you aware that Insects are rich in protein and fat content
11	Are you aware that Biowaste is a resource for recycled plant nutrients that can replace mineral fertilizers
12	Do you agree on the following statements: The community needs new products and solutions for a more effective utilisation of biowaste
13	Do you agree on the following statements: I am ready to change my eating habits and eat proteins from new sources
14	Do you agree on the following statements: We need new protein sources for humans
15	Do you agree on the following statements: We need new fertilizer sources for food production
16	Do you agree on the following statements: The European Union should be more self-sufficient in sustainable protein production
17	Do you agree on the following statements: Biowaste should be used as a source for feed
18	Do you agree on the following statements: Biowaste should be used as a source for food

19	Do you agree on the following statements: Biowaste should be used as a source for fertilizer
20	Do you agree on the following statements: Separate collection of biowaste is important
21	Do you agree on the following statements: The society should contribute to economic development/investments for more sustainable use of biowaste
22	Do you agree on the following statements: I get enough information on waste management issues, such as new policies and trends, or how to reduce waste
23	Do you take any kind of measures to palliate the climate change?
24	a) If Yes to previous, do you take these measures to palliate the climate change: reusing, recycling, reducing your waste at home
25	b) If Yes to previous, do you take these measures to palliate the climate change: I reduce water and/or energy consumption
26	c) If Yes to previous, do you take these measures to palliate the climate change: I use the public transport or alternative transport (bike, electric scooter, skateboard, roller skates etc)
27	d) If Yes to previous, do you take these measures to palliate the climate change: other ways of reducing waste
28	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Air pollution
29	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Water pollution
30	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Food security
31	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Loss of biodiversity
32	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Deforestation
33	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Waste disposal
34	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Natural resource depletion
35	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Soil degradation
36	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Water scarcity
37	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Human rights
38	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Working conditions/Health and safety
39	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Cultural heritage
40	Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues: Socio-economic impacts
41	Would you agree to choose from the following new protein or fertilizer sources when made available: Feed Protein produced by using insects
42	Would you agree to choose from the following new protein or fertilizer sources when made available: Feed Protein produced by using bacteria
43	Would you agree to choose from the following new protein or fertilizer sources when made available: Feed Protein produced by using fungi
44	Would you agree to choose from the following new protein or fertilizer sources when made available: Food Protein produced by using insects
45	Would you agree to choose from the following new protein or fertilizer sources when made available: Food Protein produced by using bacteria

46	Would you agree to choose from the following new protein or fertilizer sources when made available: Food Protein produced by using fungi
47	Would you agree to choose from the following new protein or fertilizer sources when made available: Recycled plant nutrients from biowaste
48	Have you bought products which contain insect/bacteria-based products, for example, protein bars or protein powder
49	Please, rate the following statement: The information provided on new products, such as protein bars containing insects-based ingredients, in product labels is clear, understandable and useful?
50	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Taste of the product
51	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Information on the product, for example, protein, fat or other content
52	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Functionality, referring to the main function of the product
53	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Technical quality, such as stability, durability, ease of maintenance
54	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Additional services rendered during use and disposal
55	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Aesthetics, such as appearance and design of package
56	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Image (of the product or the producer)
57	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Costs related to purchase, use and disposal
58	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Specific environmental and social properties
59	Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product: Rich vitamin and minerals content
60	Please, rate the following statements on insect/bacteria-based recycled products: Would you agree to buy insects-based products because they are sustainably produced and reduce environmental emissions?
61	Please, rate the following statements on insect/bacteria-based recycled products: Would you be willing to pay more on insect/bacteria-based protein products because their cause less environmental effects like carbon emissions, or due to functional properties, for example, positive effects on health?
62	Please, rate the following statements on insect/bacteria-based recycled products: The origin of the biowaste/side stream (= what the bacteria or insects uses) has an effect on my choice when choosing the product
63	Please, rate the following statements on insect/bacteria-based recycled products: Would you buy the insect/bacteria-based product because of rich vitamin and mineral content?

64	Please, rate the following statements on new, innovative recycled plant nutrients which are aimed at plant production: Would you agree to buy recycled plant nutrients for crop production because they are sustainably produced and reduce environmental emissions, or improve soil properties?
65	Please, rate the following statements on new, innovative recycled plant nutrients which are aimed at plant production: Would you be willing to pay more on recycled plant nutrients for crop production because their cause less environmental effects like carbon emissions?
66	Please, rate the following statements on new, innovative recycled plant nutrients which are aimed at plant production: The origin of the recycled plant nutrients for crop production has an effect on my choice when choosing the product
67	How do you think the EU and governments should motivate customers to choose recycled products: By providing information to the public on benefits
68	How do you think the EU and governments should motivate customers to choose recycled products: By lowering taxes of insect/bacteria-based products
69	How do you think the EU and governments should motivate customers to choose recycled products: By reducing inhibitory regulations
70	Please give any additional comments (hidden due to text, instead of fixed choice)

9 Annex II. The VALUEWASTE Survey questionnaire with basic report on social acceptance.

N = 523 respondents

1. Country of residence

Number of respondents: 523

Table 6: question 1, country

	n	Percent
Denmark	225	43.0%
Spain	279	53.4%
Other, which	19	3.6%

Table 7: Answers given into text field:

Option names	Text
Other, which	Belgium
Other, which	United Kingdom
Other, which	UK
Other, which	Italia
Other, which	Colombia
Other, which	Grønland
Other, which	Italy
Other, which	USA
Other, which	Germany
Other, which	France
Other, which	Francia
Other, which	Polonia
Other, which	Greece
Other, which	Australien
Other, which	Chile
Other, which	Estonia
Other, which	Greece

2. Education level

Number of respondents: 523

Table 8: question 2, education level

	Elementary/High school	Technical/vocational program	Bachelor	Master/PhD	Other/No answer	Average	Median
Please select your education level	5.2%	16.1%	21.8%	51.6%	5.3%	3.4	4.0

3. Gender

Number of respondents: 523

Table 9: question 3, gender

Female	Male	No answer	Average	Median
60.6%	39.0%	0.4%	1.4	1.0

4. Age group

Number of respondents: 523

Table 10: question 4, age group

	n	Percent
<18	4	0.8%
18-30	97	18.5%
31-45	219	41.9%
46-65	181	34.6%
>65	20	3.8%

No answer

2

0.4%

5. Are you aware that...?

Number of respondents: 523

Table 11: question 5, awareness

	Yes	No	Average	Median
the EU aims to be climate-neutral by 2050 – an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions (CO2). All parts of society and economic sectors will play a role – from the power sector to industry, mobility, buildings, agriculture and forestry	70.7%	29.3%	1.3	1.0
Technologies using insects for protein production can cause less greenhouse gas emissions than traditional methods	56.5%	43.5%	1.4	1.0
Insects are rich in protein and fat content	84.1%	15.9%	1.2	1.0

Biowaste is a resource for recycled plant nutrients that can replace mineral fertilizers	89.2%	10.8%	1.1	1.0
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6. Do you agree on the following statements?

Number of respondents: 523

Table 12: question 6, agreement with statements

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Average	Median
The community needs new products and solutions for a more effective utilisation of biowaste	4.4%	1.2%	3.6%	29.5%	61.3%	4.4	5.0
I am ready to change my eating habits and eat proteins from new sources	4.2%	10.4%	24.0%	35.0%	26.4%	3.7	4.0
We need new protein sources for humans	2.5%	5.4%	16.1%	37.8%	38.2%	4.0	4.0
We need new fertilizer sources for food production	1.5%	0.8%	8.8%	25.2%	63.7%	4.5	5.0
The European Union should be more self-sufficient in sustainable protein production	2.5%	2.7%	14.5%	33.1%	47.2%	4.2	4.0
Biowaste should be used as a source for feed	6.2%	12.9%	20.8%	31.4%	28.7%	3.6	4.0
Biowaste should be used as a source for food	3.7%	7.3%	18.5%	28.3%	42.2%	4.0	4.0
Biowaste should be used as a source for fertilizer	1.5%	1.9%	5.4%	27.8%	63.4%	4.5	5.0
Separate collection of biowaste is important	1.9%	1.6%	4.4%	28.0%	64.1%	4.5	5.0
The society should contribute to economic development/investments for more sustainable use of biowaste	6.1%	21.1%	12.9%	28.2%	31.7%	3.6	4.0
I get enough information on waste management issues, such as new policies and trends, or how to reduce waste	7.6%	21.1%	19.2%	34.4%	17.7%	3.3	4.0

7. Do you take any kind of measures to palliate the climate change?

Number of respondents: 520

Table 13: question 7, measures against climate change

	n	Percent
Yes	499	96.0%
No	21	4.0%

8. If yes, please select of the following options

Number of respondents: 512

Table 14: question 8, options to palliate climate change

	Yes	No	Average	Median
a) reusing, recycling, reducing your waste at home	94.3%	5.7%	1.1	1.0
b) I reduce water and/or energy consumption	90.9%	9.1%	1.1	1.0
c) I use the public transport or alternative transport (bike, electric scooter, skateboard, roller skates etc).	49.6%	50.4%	1.5	2.0
d) other ways of reducing waste	68.1%	31.9%	1.3	1.0

9. Please disagree/agree on the importance of following environmental and socio-economic issues

Number of respondents: 523

Table 15: question 9, agreement with the relelevance (or lack of relevance) of different issues

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Average	Median
Air pollution	0.0%	0.6%	3.4%	25.1%	70.9%	4.7	5.0
Water pollution	0.0%	0.0%	2.7%	23.0%	74.3%	4.7	5.0
Food security	0.0%	0.6%	5.7%	36.3%	57.4%	4.5	5.0
Loss of biodiversity	0.4%	1.0%	5.9%	24.2%	68.5%	4.6	5.0
Deforestation	0.9%	0.6%	4.6%	23.2%	70.7%	4.6	5.0
Waste disposal	0.6%	0.9%	4.8%	36.0%	57.7%	4.5	5.0
Natural resource depletion	0.4%	0.4%	4.0%	22.0%	73.2%	4.7	5.0
Soil degradation	0.4%	0.8%	9.9%	36.3%	52.6%	4.4	5.0
Water scarcity	0.6%	0.2%	4.6%	23.5%	71.1%	4.6	5.0
Human rights	0.4%	0.9%	9.0%	27.6%	62.1%	4.5	5.0
Working conditions/Health and safety	0.4%	0.6%	9.8%	36.6%	52.6%	4.4	5.0
Cultural heritage	0.6%	3.7%	21.7%	45.2%	28.8%	4.0	4.0
Socio-economic impacts	0.4%	2.9%	19.6%	42.6%	34.5%	4.1	4.0

10. Would you agree to choose from the following new protein or fertilizer sources when made available?

Number of respondents: 523

Table 16: question 10, new protein or fertiliser sources preferences

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Average	Median
Feed Protein produced by using insects	2.7%	5.2%	11.5%	39.4%	41.2%	4.1	4.0
Feed Protein produced by using bacteria	1.6%	7.5%	23.4%	34.2%	33.3%	3.9	4.0
Feed Protein produced by using fungi	1.3%	4.3%	18.0%	36.0%	40.4%	4.1	4.0
Food Protein produced by using insects	7.9%	13.5%	24.5%	30.4%	23.7%	3.5	4.0
Food Protein produced by using bacteria	5.4%	12.8%	31.3%	30.1%	20.4%	3.5	4.0
Food Protein produced by using fungi	3.9%	7.8%	23.7%	34.7%	29.9%	3.8	4.0
Recycled plant nutrients from biowaste	3.9%	6.9%	15.0%	32.7%	41.5%	4.0	4.0

11. Have you bought products which contain insect/bacteria-based products, for example, protein bars or protein powder

Number of respondents: 515

Table 17: question 11, bought products

	n	Percent
Yes	97	18.8%
No	418	81.2%

12. Please, rate the following statement

Number of respondents: 506

Table 18: question 12, agreement with an statement

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Average	Median
The information provided on new products, such as protein bars containing insects- based ingredients, in product labels clear, understandable and useful?	2.8%	6.5%	49.0%	19.4%	22.3%	3.5	3.0

13. Please evaluate the importance of following properties of the insect/bacteria-based product

Number of respondents: 505

Table 19: question 13, ingredients properties relevance

	Not important at all	No much importance	Neutral	Some importance	Very high importance	Average	Median
Taste of the product	2.2%	0.6%	14.5%	29.5%	53.2%	4.3	5.0
Information on the product, for example, protein, fat or other content	1.4%	1.4%	12.6%	38.0%	46.6%	4.3	4.0
Functionality, referring to the main function of the product	1.6%	1.6%	17.2%	41.5%	38.1%	4.1	4.0
Technical quality, such as stability, durability, ease of maintenance	1.4%	1.8%	15.4%	43.5%	37.9%	4.1	4.0
Additional services rendered during use and disposal	1.8%	4.8%	27.1%	41.0%	25.3%	3.8	4.0
Aesthetics, such as appearance and design of package	6.8%	15.5%	32.6%	28.8%	16.3%	3.3	3.0
Image (of the product or the producer)	4.8%	8.3%	27.8%	37.8%	21.3%	3.6	4.0
Costs related to purchase, use and disposal	1.4%	4.6%	20.5%	42.2%	31.3%	4.0	4.0
Specific environmental and social properties	1.8%	2.8%	18.4%	39.3%	37.7%	4.1	4.0
Rich vitamin and minerals content	2.2%	3.0%	14.8%	39.0%	41.0%	4.1	4.0

14. Please, rate the following statements on insect/bacteria-based recycled products

Number of respondents: 514

Table 20: question 14, statements relevance

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Average	Median
Would you agree to buy insects-based products because they are sustainably produced and reduce environmental emissions?	8.2%	8.6%	20.0%	40.1%	23.1%	3.6	4.0

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Average	Median
Would you be willing to pay more on insect/bacteria-based protein products because their cause less environmental effects like carbon emissions, or due to functional properties, for example, positive effects on health?	13.1%	20.3%	25.9%	29.6%	11.1%	3.1	3.0
The origin of the biowaste/side stream (= what the bacteria or insects uses) has an effect on my choice when choosing the product	4.5%	9.4%	31.4%	35.8%	18.9%	3.6	4.0
Would you buy the insect/bacteria-based product because of rich vitamin and mineral content?	9.4%	11.6%	25.7%	39.6%	13.7%	3.4	4.0

15. Please, rate the following statements on new, innovative recycled plant nutrients which are aimed at plant production

Number of respondents: 515

Table 21: question 15, statements rating

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Average	Median
Would you agree to buy recycled plant nutrients for crop production because they are sustainably produced and reduce environmental emissions, or improve soil properties?	2.2%	1.2%	13.1%	39.9%	43.6%	4.2	4.0
Would you be willing to pay more	6.0%	14.0%	22.6%	38.3%	19.1%	3.5	4.0

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Average	Median
on recycled plant nutrients for crop production because their cause less environmental effects like carbon emissions?							
The origin of the recycled plant nutrients for crop production has an effect on my choice when choosing the product	2.7%	5.3%	26.4%	42.6%	23.0%	3.8	4.0

16. How do you think the EU and governments should motivate customers to choose recycled products

Number of respondents: 517

Table 22: question 16, how the EU Commission should motivate customers

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Average	Median
By providing information to the public on benefits	2.5%	1.4%	5.0%	38.5%	52.6%	4.4	5.0
By lowering taxes of insect/bacteria-based products	2.9%	3.9%	10.8%	35.3%	47.1%	4.2	4.0
By reducing inhibitory regulations	3.3%	5.3%	24.6%	35.0%	31.8%	3.9	4.0

